

RESEARCH ARTICLE

An Assessment of the Perception of Environmental Sanitation and Solid Waste Management Service Delivery in AMAC, Abuja, Central Nigeria

IMANFIDON, Samson Enehizenan¹ and AGBEBAKU, Henry Usiobaifo²

¹Department of Geography and Environmental Management, Faculty of Environmental Studies, Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma, Edo State, Nigeria. E-mail: imanfidonsamson70@aauekpoma.edu.ng.

²Department of Environmental science, Faculty of Environmental science, National Open University (NOUN), Nigeria. E-mail: hagbebaku@noun.edu.ng.

Abstract

The study assesses the perception of environmental sanitation and solid waste management service delivery in Abuja Municipal Area Council, (AMAC), Abuja. A total of 1056 structured questionnaires were distributed randomly to obtain information from the respondents. This was complemented with oral interviews and focus group discussion with stakeholders like staff of Abuja Environmental Protection Board (AEPB) and household heads. Simple descriptive statistics was used in the presentation and analysis of the data obtained. It is evident from the study that socio-economic characteristics such as income and education greatly influenced the quantity of waste generation. The outcome of the interview on staff of AEPB revealed that the agency is only responsible for the collection, transportation and disposal of the waste to the approved government sites and that the informal waste collectors are only interested in the recyclables; leaving the main waste unattended to for days and weeks. The study recommends reduction and prevention of wastes at source, landfill reduction and diversion by investing in advanced waste management technologies, leveraging technology and innovative waste collection systems which involves the utilization of digital systems or platforms to optimize waste collection routes, track waste generation, and monitor recycling rates and finally aggressive public awareness and education by engaging with communities, schools, businesses to promote best practice waste management and encourage responsible waste disposal was canvassed. This can foster a culture of sustainability as well as empower individual to become an active member and participant in the waste management chain or reduction efforts.

Keywords: Assessment, perception, environmental, sanitation, solid waste, management delivery

1. Introduction

Solid waste management has become a major challenge facing developing countries. It appears the reality of development and the associated problems were not prepared for in this part of the world, hence nations, states, regions and local communities are unable to match the volume of solid wastes being generated. Environmental protection agencies at all levels in Nigeria are overwhelmed as the waste management problems are faster than the ability of the agencies to improve on both the financial and technical resources needed to handle the problems from generation, collection, transportation and disposal of these wastes.

In its modern concept, environment includes not only water, air and soil but also the social and economic conditions under which we live (Park, 2011). The key to man's health lies largely in his

environment. In fact, much of man's ill-health can be traced to adverse environmental factors such as water, soil and air pollution, poor housing conditions, presence of animal reservoir and insect vectors of diseases which pose threats to man's health. Often, man is responsible for the pollution of his environment through urbanization, industrialization and other human activities.

According to the National Sanitation Foundation of USA, the word sanitation is defined as a „way of life that is expressed in the clean home, farm, business, neighborhoods and community (Park, 2011). Also, World Health Organization (WHO) defines sanitation as the provision of facilities and services for the safe disposal of human urine and faeces (UNICEF AND WHO, 2012). The word 'sanitation' also refers to the maintenance of hygienic conditions through services such as garbage collection and wastewater disposal. In addition, environmental sanitation according to World Health Organization is the control of all those factors in man's physical environment which exercise or may exercise a deleterious effect on his physical development, health and survival. It could also be seen as the principle and practice of effecting healthful and hygienic conditions in the environment to promote public health and welfare, improve quality of life and ensure a sustainable environment (Alabi, 2010). Where land tenure status is murky, many residents live on rented or squatted land, which makes it impossible for them to make any decisions regarding the development or use of the land (Corburn, Karanja, (2016) and Awunyo-Akaba, et al.(2016).

2. Statement of the Problem

As humanity continues to chase development to improve their lives, cities around the world are facing huge wastes problems. While urbanization is undeniably a product of economic and commercial growth, it also carries with it unique challenges and environmental one in particular. Increasing waste generation is a factor that is directly tied to urbanization in this days and age. The huge volume of waste generated by urban population couple with poor infrastructures in terms of equipments, technical knowhow and finances has created a perfect storm for environmental and public health crisis.

Many cities all over the world including Nigeria struggle with insufficient waste collection systems, leading to overflowing bins, gutters, littering and the formation of unsightly dumpsites. This is coupled with the problem of transportation of wastes to processing facilities which is often insufficient, contributing to traffic congestion, foul smells, air pollution and its associated diseases and other ill health conditions. There is therefore the need to assess this problem with a view to finding lasting solutions.

2.1. Objectives of the study

The aim is to examine the perception of sanitary and waste management service delivery in AMAC, Abuja and the objectives are to:

1. identifies the main factors contributing to the problem of waste management in AMAC, Abuja.
2. Assess the level of promptness in the evacuation of waste in AMAC, Abuja.
3. Examine the compliance level of AMAC residence to sanitation and waste management indicators in Abuja.
4. Suggest strategies for improving the efficiency and management of solid waste management in AMAC, Abuja.

3. Literature review

The essential components of environmental sanitation include: solid waste management; medical waste management; excreta and sewage management; food sanitation; sanitary inspection of premises; market and abattoir sanitation; adequate potable water supply; school sanitation; pest and vector control; management of urban drainage; control of reared and stray animals; disposal of the dead animals; weed

and vegetation control; hygiene education and promotion. Hence, inadequate sanitation is a major cause of disease world-wide and improving sanitation is known to have a significant beneficial impact on health both in households and across communities (Alabi, 2010, UNICEF and WHO, 2012).

In most developing countries adequate environmental sanitation has not been strictly adhered to. For example, in some parts of Nigeria, living with waste as part of the natural environment has become a way of life even in the state capitals including parts of Abuja. Although there has been a remarkable improvement from what it used to be in the late eighties and early nineties, there is still much to be done as Lagos, our “Nigerian Centre of Excellence”, has been depicted a vast slum (Alabi, 2010). In the United States, slum is often used to refer to marginalized neighborhoods, but in developing countries and Nigeria in particular, it usually means a settlement built in or near a city by residents themselves, without official authorization or regulation. Such housing units are typically substandard, and the infrastructure and services range from non-existent to improvised.

Furthermore, environmental hazards are responsible for about a quarter of the total burden of disease worldwide and as much as 30% in regions such as sub-Saharan Africa. As many as 13 million deaths can be prevented every year by making our environments healthier (WHO, 2012). These facts and figures highlight the impact of environmental factors on public health. More than 2.4 billion people in the world currently lack access to adequate sanitation and are forced to dispose of their excreta in unimproved and unsanitary conditions. Those who suffer from this, lack most basic human needs and also tend to be victims of poverty, ill health and an overall poor quality of life (WHO, 2013).

Succinctly, each of these potential solutions to addressing problems would become formalized as a policy response through new legislative amendments, to existing legislation and program directives or the creation of a special initiatives or funds, if the legislative base is already in place (Oaikhena, 2023). According to United Nations report of 2019, 4.2 billion people live without safely-managed sanitation; 673 million practice open defecation and 3 billion lack basic hand-washing facilities. The Impact of these practices has huge impact on household’s health and wellbeing globally and Nigeria inclusive. According to the same report, economically; about 1.3% (N455 billion) of Gross Domestic Product (GDP) is lost every year to poor sanitation and open defecation. Health wise, over 100,000 children under five years of age die annually of diarrheal diseases, directly attributed to unsafe water and sanitation. The diseases contracted from water contaminated by faeces leads to stunted growth and malnutrition in children. In the same report, 4.2 billion people live without proper sanitation. The same report pointed out that 673 million people still practice open defecation all over the world. As a result, about 2 billion people use a drinking water source contaminated with faeces globally. This leads to 432,000 diarrhea deaths and contributes to diseases like intestinal worms.

Poor sanitation access in informal settlements is caused by several factors, including inadequate infrastructure and lack of proper planning (Sprouse, et al. 2024), Corburn, Sverdlik, (2019), and Cheng, S. (2024). In the absence of accessible sanitation infrastructure and waste disposal mechanisms, open defecation and improper waste disposal become common practices, resulting in contamination of drinking water sources and the spread of diseases (Mara, D. 2017) Prüss-Ustün, et al. (2019) Manga, et al. (2022). In many places shared sanitation facilities have been effective in improving sanitation access, replacing open defecation (Schelbert, et al. 2021 and Lebu, et al.,2024), which is much more detrimental to public and environmental health. Provision of individual household toilets can be challenging and unfeasible in places with high population density, insufficient space, high capital costs, and the quantity of water required to operate most sanitation systems efficiently. In such conditions, high-quality shared toilets may be the most viable option for extending sanitation services to residents (Evans, et al (2017), Ross, et al (2022), Schelbert, et al (2021), Lebu, et al. (2024) and Tidwell, et al (2021). Here in Nigeria, back in 2018, Water, Sanitation and Hygiene (WASH) National Outcome Routine Mapping (WASH NORM) carried out a survey and found that Nigeria ranks second among countries practicing open defecation across the world. Findings from the survey show that 24% of the population (47 million people) still practice open defecation. This means one in four Nigerians defecates outside. Even though

this may be doubtful, yet, it calls for a serious concern and demands that the authority should declare a state of emergency to end this so as to avoid its consequences. As of 2022, it is estimated that 570 million people shared sanitation facilities with other households (UNICEF & WHO, 2023). Considering that sharing of sanitation facilities is likely to be higher in urban slums and other high-density informal settlements with inadequate services (Heijnen, Rosa, Fuller, Eisenberg, & Clasen, (2014) households in informal settlements likely make up a large proportion of this estimate. It is also common for multiple households to share sanitation facilities in planned residential areas (Foggitt, Cawood,, Evans, & Acheampong, 2019) It has been reported that communal living is prevalent in many urban areas in low- and middle-income countries (LMICs), where up to 80 families live together in a compound and share sanitation, cooking, and other facilities (Bateganya,, et al.2023) Research indicates that nearly one in five people in Sub-Saharan Africa (18%) and Eastern Asia (19%) use shared sanitation; it is especially common in Ghana (59%), Congo, and Gabon (both 34%) Foggitt, Cawood, Evans, & Acheampong, (2019) Antwi-Agyei, Monney, Amaning Adjei, Kweyu, & Simiyu, (2022) and Kabange, Graham, & Nkansah, (2016).

In developing countries like Nigeria, the main diseases of the environment are diarrhea, lower respiratory infections, unintentional injuries, and malaria. In children under the age of five, one third of all disease is caused by the environmental factors such as unsafe water and air pollution (WHO, 2010). Deaths resulting from diarrhea are estimated to be between 1.6 and 2.5 million every year (WHO, 2012). National records show that every year, about six hundred thousand (600,000) episodes of diarrhea occur in children under the age of five (Alabi, 2010).

According to Olu-Sule (2003) housing quality goes beyond the building materials to include availability of water for the toilets, kitchen and bathing facilities. He stressed that the supply of water for sewage systems and residential amenities enhances housing quality. Olu-Sule maintained that environmental problems created by poor water supply to such housing facilities like sewage, toilets, bathroom and kitchen in the urban centres are vexing and that poor water supply to some facilities cause health problems and increase the per capital expenditure on medical service delivery in the country. According to Olu-Sule (2003), house hygiene quality is not only determined by the building materials but also by such amenities as toilets, kitchen, bathing facilities, store, water supply, electricity and sewage systems and concluded that there are amenities which enhances housing quality. Olu-Sule (2003), observed that poor building material and poor housing conditions equally manifest in filthy and stinking environment in most urban centres in Nigeria leading to the numerous problems encountered by service providers like fire fighters in providing needed services to those in need of such services.

Akinbamiro (2012) found significant relationship between health status of residents and house hygiene measured in terms of age of building, waste disposal method, frequency of collection, management of waste water, types of toilet, walling materials, type of roofing materials, adequacy of electricity, types of kitchen and state of repairs of building in Odi-Olowo residential district, Osogbo, Osun state, Nigeria and recommend public health campaign, wider coverage of waste removal agencies and public sector intervention, in improving access to housing fund for rehabilitation, innovations and redevelopment. In the same vein, (Adegbo, 1997) states that urban housing has qualitative defects with most houses lacking basic facilities. He observed that between 1992 – 1997 urban households with pit latrine accounted for 42.4%, those with water closet (wc) 0.90%, making households with toilet to be 42.94% which according to him was too low compare to Germany which has 100%, Japan 98.8% and Canada 99.6% (Federal office of statistics, 1995). Adeagbo expected that between 1997 and 2010 the proportion of household in urban areas with pit latrine will be less than 5%, while those with water closet (WC) should be at least 25%.

Similarly, Asuzu (2002), reports that unhealthy housing conditions may result in communicable and non-communicable diseases as well as psychological disorders such as insect vector diseases, rodent vector diseases, geohelminthiasis (diseases due to animal faeces) diseases due to animal bites, neuroses, violence, delinquency drug and alcohol abuse, heart disease, cancer etc. In this study, household

hygiene, sanitation and waste management service delivery will be measured with the following indices; water availability, availability of water storage tank, types of toilets, availability of bathroom, kitchen availability, refuse disposal types, availability of mosquito nets on doors and windows, sanitary waste bins, waste disposal system, distance between house and waste receptacle points, and number of persons sleeping in the same room per night.

4. Data Presentation and Analysis

Bio-data and major socio-economic variables of the respondents (sex, education, occupation and annual income) are hereby summarized as contained in the table.

Table 1. Socio-economic status of Respondents in AMAC.

Variable	Respondents	Percentage (%)
Sex		
Male	1001	94.79
Female	55	5.21
Total	1056	100
Education		
Primary	35	3.3
Secondary	415	39.3
Tertiary	606	57.4
TOTAL	1,056	100
OCCUPATION		
Office	609	57.8
Artisans	164	15.5
Transportation	103	9.7
Politics	180	17.0
TOTAL	1,056	100
ANNUAL INCOME		
Less Than 216,000	47	4.5
217,000 – 432,000	76	7.2
433,000 – 648,000	113	11.0
649,000 – 864,000	320	30.0
865,000 & Above	500	47.3
TOTAL	1,056	100.0

Source: Field Work, 2025

Table 1.1 shows information on sex, of the respondents. From the Table, out of 1,056 respondents, 1001(94.79%) are male while 55 (5.21%) are female. The table also clearly proved that, majority of the household heads in the study area is males.

Table 1.1 also shows the educational attainment of the respondents which are: (primary, secondary and tertiary). From the Table, 35 (3.3%) have primary education, 415(39.3%) have secondary education, while 606 (57.4%) have qualifications above secondary school. It is evident from the Table that a higher number of the respondents are enlightened since 87% of them have education higher than secondary school.

Still on socio-economic characteristics, Table 1.1 contains the result of the occupational structure of the respondents. As can be seen, 609 (57.7%) are engaged in office work, 164 representing (15.5%) are

artisans, 103 (9.8%) are transporters; while 180 (17.0%) are politicians. It is also evident from the Table that 75% of them are engaged in office works and politics whereas only 25% are engaged in artisan and transportation business. See Table 1.1.

On the annual income of respondents, table 1.1 shows the respondents annual income, based on the approved national minimum wage. Four categories of income bracket were identified. Those whose annual income is N216,000 are 47(4.5%) only. Annual incomes of between N217,000–N432,000 are 76(7.2%). Those within N433,000–N648,000 constituted 113 (10.7%) and those earning between 649,000–864,000 are 320(30.3%); while those earning N865,000 and above are 500(47.3%). The Table equally shows that majority of the respondents earns over and above N801,000 per annum.

Table 1.2 shows the various sources of water in the study area which were categorized into five (pipe borne water, private borehole, water vendors/well, rivers/streams and others such as pond and underground tank). From the result, only 311(29.5%) of the respondents use pipe borne water; 407 (38.5%) patronizes private boreholes, 307 (29.1%) are patronizing water vendors/well whereas the other 31 (3%) are getting water either from rivers, streams, ponds, rain water and underground tanks.

Table 2. Sources of Water.

Source of water	No of respondents	Percentage (%)
Pipe borne water	311	29.5
Private borehole	407	38.5
Water vendor/well	307	29.1
River/stream	28	2.7
Others (pond/rain water etc)	3	0.3
Total	1056	100.0

Source: Field work, 2025

The researcher equally sought to know the availability of water storage tanks in the households. From table 3. 928 (87.9%) have water storage tank while 128(12.1%) do not have. A household is required to have between 3000-5000 litres of water storage tank both for domestic and for emergencies such as house fire (WHO, 2004). Analysis of availability of water storage tank in the households showed that this facility is available in (88%) of the households and unavailable in (12%) cases. Apart from drinking water, households are expected to have between (500-1000) litres of water to be used for such emergencies as house fire particularly those who have no access to pipe borne water in their home (WHO, 2004). In AMAC, it was discovered that only (12%) are not ready for such emergencies which suggests that majority of AMAC residents have complied with best practices as recommended. From the table, it can be concluded that water tanks are available in most households as shown in Table.

[Image of a domestic water storage and filtration system diagram]

Table 3. Availability of water storage tank in the household.

Availability of storage tank	No of respondents	Percentage (%)
Available	928	87.9
Not available	128	12.1
Total	1056	100.0

Source: Field work, 2025

Table 4 shows the result of the responses on the use of warm and cold bathe facilities in the study area. From the table, 523 constituting (49.5%) attested to having access to warm or cold bathe whereas 533 (50.5%) do not have such facility either as a result of poor light supply in their area or inability to afford such facility.

Table 4. *Availability of Warm and Cold Bathe Facilities.*

Availability of warm/cold bathe	No of respondents	Percentage (%)
Available	523	49.5
Not available	533	50.5
Total	1056	100.0

Source: Field work, 2025

The researcher also sought to know whether the respondents have mosquito net for their doors and windows which will help them to prevent mosquito bite that could lead to frequent disease condition such as malaria. From table 5, 1,022 (96.8%) respondents have mosquito nets on their doors and windows whereas only 34(3.2%) do not have such facility. On a general note, one could see from the table that the people's awareness on the importance of mosquito net was high.

Table 5. *Availability of Mosquito Nets for Door/Windows.*

Availability of mosquito net	No of respondents	Percentage (%)
Available	1022	96.8
Not available	34	3.2
Total	1056	100.0

Source: Field work, 2025

Table 6 shows the number of households having sanitary waste bin. From the table, 900 (85.2%) respondents have sanitary waste bin and 156 (14.8%) do not. This is quite significant as most of the households have sanitary waste bins where waste are kept outside their houses making most households free from poor hygiene related diseases such as dysentery, diarrhoea, cholera irritation among others.

Table 6. *Availability of Sanitary Waste Bin.*

Availability of sanitary waste bin	No of respondents	Percent
Available	900	85.2
Not available	156	14.8
Total	1056	100.0

Source: Field work, 2025

Table 7 shows waste disposal system available in the study area. From the table, majority of the respondents 601 (56.9%) use authorized vendors to dispose of their wastes; 251 (23.8%) disposed their wastes themselves while 139 (13.2%) patronizes unauthorized waste vendors whereas 65(6.2) use other means by either throwing it anywhere of by burying it within. The result in table 7 presents to us that only 57% of the respondents dispose their waste through approved means while 53% of them do so illegally.

Source: Field work, 2025

Table 7. Waste disposal system available.

Waste disposal system	No of respondents	Percentage (%)
Unauthorized Waste vendors	139	13.2
Authorized waste vendors	601	56.9
Self help	251	23.8
Others (thrown away/buried within)	65	6.2
Total	1056	100.0

Table 8 presents the distance between waste collection points and residential buildings in the study area. In line with Abuja building regulations, the distance between buildings and waste collection point should not be more than 100 metres. However, Table 1.8 shows that 675(64%) are within hundred meters while 381 (36%) have to cover more than a hundred meter to get to waste collection point.

Table 8. Distance between residential building and waste collection point.

Distance between waste collection points and households	No of respondents	Percentage (%)
Less than 100 meters	675	63.9
More than 100 meters	381	36.1
Total	1056	100.0

Source: Field work, 2025

Table 9 shows the result of the responses on availability of store in the household. From the table, 565 (53.5%) have store whereas 491 (46.5%) do not. Quite surprising is the fact that as high as 491 (47%) household still do not have store for storing food and food items are rather kept in the kitchen making the kitchen so congested and providing safe haven for rodents and cockroaches which are disease vectors.

Table 9. Availability of Store for Food Storage in the home.

Store for food storage	No of respondents	Percentage (%)
Available	565	53.5
Not available	491	46.5
Total	1056	100.0

Source: Field work, 2025

Table 10 shows the regularity of waste collection by the authority concerned. From the table, only 36 (3.4%) claimed that wastes were evacuated daily. Those who opined that wastes are collected on a weekly basis are 365 (34.6%), bi-weekly 45 (4.3%), monthly basis 438 (41.5%) while those whose wastes are not evacuated at all by government agencies are 172 (16.2%).

Source: Field work, 2025

Table 11 presents the result on waste management service delivery. From the table, 622 (59%) are satisfied while 434 (41%) are dissatisfied. From what can be seen in the Table, most of the households in AMAC are satisfied with the services of waste managers. Nevertheless, the 41% who are dissatisfied are not insignificant to be ignored in a place like AMAC. This percentage numbers reserve the same right to healthy environment and prompt removal of wastes as they pay for this services which are poorly rendered.

Table 10. *Regularity of Waste evacuation by government agencies.*

Category	Frequency/service delivery	Percent (%)
Daily	36	3.4
Weekly	365	34.6
bi-weekly	45	4.3
Monthly	438	41.5
Not at all	172	16.2
Total	1056	100.0

Table 11. *Waste Management Service delivery.*

Level of satisfaction	No of respondents	Percentage (%)
Very satisfied	11	1.0
Satisfied	281	26.6
Fairly satisfied	330	31.3
Dissatisfied	311	29.5
Very dissatisfied	123	11.6
Total	1056	100.0

Source: Field work, 2025

Table 12 shows the incidences and cases of members of households having pneumonia in the study area. From the table, only 147 (14%) of the respondents claim to have frequent cases of pneumonia while 909 (86%) are free from such health condition. This implies that the disease condition called pneumonia is not common in the study area. This also suggests that the people are conscious of the actions and inactions that expose one to such disease condition.

Table 12. *Incidence of a member of a household having Pneumonia.*

Incidences of pneumonia	No of respondents	Percentage (%)
No. of respondents suffering from Pneumonia	147	13.9
No. of respondents not suffering from Pneumonia	909	86.1
Total	1056	100.0

Source: Field work, 2025

Table 13 presents the result of the spread of Malaria fever in the study area. From the table, 659(62%) attests to no cases of malaria fever while 397 (38%) says they do have malaria fever in the study area. This shows that majority of the residence may have taken the necessary precautions that could make them vulnerable to malaria such as covering their windows, doors as well as their bed with mosquito net at night. The Table equally shows that though the numbers of people without the disease condition are more, a significant number (37.6%) have it as shown in Table 13.

Table 13. *Incidences of members of household having malaria fever.*

Incidences/cases of Malaria	No of respondents	Percentage (%)
Cases/incidences of Malaria	397	37.6
No. cases/incidences of Malaria	659	62.4
Total	1056	100.0

Source: Field work, 2025

Table 14 shows the result of the disease conditions common in the study area. From the table 575 (55%) are affected by typhoid, 281 (27%) have cough and cold, 32 (3%) have pneumonia, 20 (2%) have arthritis, 35 (3%) have asthma/ respiratory diseases. Other diseases in the study area are: TB, dysentery etc and it accounted for (11%). The Table equally shows that AMAC residence have quite a number of diseases to contend with.

Table 14. Disease condition common in the study area/vicinity.

Disease common in the study area	No of respondents	Percentage (%)
Typhoid	575	54.5
Cough and cold	281	26.6
Hiv/Aids	32	3.0
Arthritis	20	1.9
Asthma/respiratory disease	35	3.3
Others(TB, Dysentery) etc.	113	10.7
Total	1056	100.0

Source: Field work, 2025

Table 15 is the result of the number of residences experiencing flooding during the wet seasons. From the table, it is clear that majority of the households 840 (79.5%) do not experience flooding. However, 216 (20.5%) experienced flooding in the study area. This suggests that AMAC is well drained and most of the inhabitants are complying with rules that could encourage good drainage and prevent flooding such as cleaning of gutter, dumping of refuse in authorized places for easy evacuation.

Table 15. Flooding during wet /rainy Season.

Flooding during wet season	No of respondents	Percentage (%)
Flooding	216	20.5
No flooding	840	79.5
Total	1056	100.0

Source: Field work, 2025

Table 16 shows the result of closeness of residential dwellings to stagnant water. As can be seen, the table shows that 268 (25%) have stagnant water nearby while 788 representing (75%) are not close to stagnant water. Again, this suggests that AMAC is well drained.

Table 16. Nearness/closeness to stagnant Water.

Nearness/closeness water to stagnant	No of respondents	Percentage (%)
Yes	268	25.4
No	788	74.6
Total	1056	100.0

Source: Field work, 2025

Table 17 shows the various sources of water in the study area which were categorized into five (pipe borne water, private borehole, water vendors/well, rivers/streams and others such as pond and underground tank). From the result, only 311(29.5%) of the respondents use pipe borne water; 407 (38.5%) patronizes private boreholes, 307 (29.1%) are patronizing water vendors/well whereas the other 31 (3%) are getting water either from rivers, streams, ponds, rain water and underground tanks.

Table 17. *Sources of Water (Verification).*

Source of water	No of respondents	Percentage (%)
Piped water	311	29.5
Private borehole	407	38.5
water vendor/well	307	29.1
River/stream	28	2.7
Others(pond/rain water etc)	3	0.3
Total	1056	100.0

Source: Field work, 2025

From table 18, 928 (87.9%) have water storage tank while 128(12.1%) do not have. A household is required to have between 3000-5000 litres tank of water both for domestic and for emergencies such as house fire (WHO, 2004). From the table, it can be concluded that water tanks are available in most households as shown in Table 1.18.

Table 18. *Availability of water storage tank in the household (Verification).*

Availability of storage tank	No of respondents	Percentage (%)
Available	928	87.9
Not available	128	12.1
Total	1056	100.0

Source: Field work, 2025

Table 19 shows the result of the responses on the use of warm and cold bathe facilities in the study area. From the table, 523 constituting (49.5%) attested to having access to warm or cold bathe whereas 533 (50.5%) do not have such facility either as a result of poor light supply in their area or inability to afford such facility.

Table 19. *Availability of Warm and Cold Bathe Facilities (Verification).*

Availability of warm/cold bathe	No of respondents	Percentage (%)
Available	523	49.5
Not available	533	50.5
Total	1056	100.0

Source: Field work, 2025

With regards to types of toilet facilities in houses in the study area, four types were identified (water closet, pit latrine, public toilet and nearby bush/open defecation). From Table 1.20, 1008 (96%)

have water closet (WC) and the remaining 48 (4%) are either using pit latrine, public toilets or nearby bush/open defecation. This result shows that majority of the respondents are using modern toilet facilities.

Table 20. *Type of Toilet Facilities in the home.*

Types of toilets	No of respondents	Percentage (%)
Water closet	1008	95.5
Pit latrine	14	1.3
Public toilet	7	0.7
Nearby bush/open defecation	27	2.6
Total	1056	100.0

Source: Field work, 2025

The researcher also sought to know whether the respondents have mosquito net for their doors and windows which will help them to prevent mosquito bite that could lead to frequent disease condition such as malaria. From table 21, 1,022 (96.8%) respondents have mosquito nets on their doors and windows whereas only 34(3.2%) do not have such facility. On a general note, one could see from the table that the people's awareness on the importance of mosquito net was high.

Table 21. *Availability of Mosquito Nets for Door/Windows (Verification).*

Availability of mosquito net	No of respondents	Percentage (%)
Available	1022	96.8
Not available	34	3.2
Total	1056	100.0

Source: Field work, 2025

Table 22, shows the number of households having sanitary waste bin. From the table, 900 (85.2%) respondents have sanitary waste bin and 156 (14.8%) do not. This is quite significant as most of the households have sanitary waste bins where waste are kept outside their houses making most households free from poor hygiene related diseases such as dysentery, diarrhoea, cholera irritation among others.

Table 22. *Availability of Sanitary Waste Bin (Verification).*

Availability of sanitary waste bin	No of respondents	Percent
Available	900	85.2
Not available	156	14.8
Total	1056	100.0

Source: Field work, 2025

Table 23 shows waste disposal system available in the study area. From the table, majority of the respondents 601 (56.9%) use authorized vendors to dispose of their wastes; 251 (23.8%) disposed their wastes themselves while 139 (13.2%) patronizes unauthorized waste vendors whereas 65(6.2) use other means by either throwing it anywhere of by burying it within. The result in table 23 presents to us that only 57% of the respondents dispose their waste through approved means while 53% of them do so illegally.

Table 23. *Waste disposal system available (Verification).*

Waste disposal system	No of respondents	Percentage (%)
Unauthorized Waste vendors	139	13.2
Authorized waste vendors	601	56.9
Self help	251	23.8
Others(thrown away/buried within)	65	6.2
Total	1056	100.0

Source: Field work, 2019

Table 24 presents the distance between waste collection points and residential buildings in the study area. In line with Abuja building regulations, the distance between buildings and waste collection point should not be more than 100 metres. However, Table 4.4.10 shows that 675(64%) are within hundred meters while 381 (36%) have to cover more than a hundred meter to get to waste collection point.

Table 24. *Distance between residential building and waste collection point (Verification).*

Distance between waste collection points and households	No of respondents	Percentage (%)
Less than 100 meters	675	63.9
More than 100 meters	381	36.1
Total	1056	100.0

Source: Field work, 2025

The table below shows the number of persons sleeping in a room per night. From the table, over 91 percent of the respondents have two or more people sleeping in a room which presupposes that there is the possibility of one contacting communicable and airborne diseases. See table below.

Table 25. *Number of Persons sleeping in a Room at Night.*

Number of persons sleeping in a room	No of respondents	Percentage (%)
One	73	6.9
Two	404	38.3
More than Two	579	54.8
Total	1056	100.0

Source: Field work, 2025

5. Summary of Findings

In summary, the paper observed that the main factors contributing to the problem of waste management in AMAC ranges from late evacuation, insufficient waste bin, water problems and unconventional means of waste disposal which is still being used in AMAC. Besides, our interaction revealed that wastes are not promptly evacuated leading to wind and vectors scattering and spreading the waste which is unhealthy for the inhabitants. Third, the paper also observed that AMAC has not yet complied to (WHO's) standards of number of people per room per night and other wastes management measures. Forth, going by the biodata of the respondents; it cuts across all the spectrum of socio-economic indicators of age, education, occupation and income distribution which show that all groups were fully represented. The paper also

shows that up to 55% of the inhabitants still suffer from typhoid which is related to consumption of bad, unhygienic and contaminated water in the study area. This may not be unconnected with the fact that a vast majority of the people up to 70% still patronize private bore holes, water vendors, streams and river whereas on 30% are depending on pipe borne water absolutely in a place like AMAC which is a microcosm of Nigeria as contained in table 17 of this article.

The paper also discovered that up to 43% of AMAC dwellers still use unconventional means in disposing their wastes and this can result to a number of environmental issues in the future such as blockage of gutters which can lead to flooding, destruction of houses and properties and other associated diseases as in table 23.

Another problem which this paper pointed out in AMAC is that of the number of people sleeping in a room per night. The World Health Organization recommended that where more than two people sleep in a room per night it is overcrowded. In AMAC, as shown in table 25; this paper observed that as high as 55% of the people living in AMAC have more than two people sleeping in a room per night. This points to the fact that there is the likelihood that there will be accommodation problem in the study area if they are not already experiencing it as suggested by this finding.

6. Conclusion And Recommendation

6.1. Conclusion

The challenges posed by waste management in AMAC are complex and multifaceted. It ranges from water shortage, unconventional waste disposal, to delay in wastes evacuation of same leading to unsatisfactory wastes evacuation as reported by residence. Collaborative measure is therefore required to tackle the problem of waste management in AMAC if the United Nation's waste management goals for sustainable development which includes diverting 75% of wastes from landfills by 2030 must be achieved.

6.2. Recommendation

1. **Reduction and prevention at source.** A key strategy in waste prevention and reduction is sustainable practices by encouraging consumers and businesses to minimize waste generation through initiative such as decomposing. By promoting sustainable consumption patterns, they contribute to reducing the overall waste burden to avoid the use of self-help methods.
2. **Landfill reduction and diversion.** Waste management authorities like Abuja Environmental Protection Agency (AEPB) should invest in advanced waste management technologies. These technologies as used in advanced countries can recover valuable materials, from wastes such as metals, plastics and paper for recycling or reuse. By diverting wastes from landfills, and extracting valuable resources, this helps conserve ecosystem and other natural resources and reduce the negative environmental impact of wastes.
3. **Leveraging technology and innovative waste collection systems.** This involves the utilization of digital systems or platforms to optimize waste collection routes, track waste generation, and monitor reclining rates. This data driven approach enables efficient waste management operations and help identify areas where possible improvements are needed.
4. **Public awareness and education.** By engaging with communities, schools, businesses can promote best practice waste management and encourage responsible waste disposal. This can foster a culture of sustainability as this can empower individual to become an active member and participant in the waste management chain or reduction efforts.
5. **Provision of water to the residence by the government** as only 30% of the population use pipe borne water. Effective sanitation requires water for cooking, bathe, flushing of toilets, washing and other domestic uses.

6. **Waste management authority** should rise to the occasion of prompt disposal of both solid and liquid wastes, make provision for adequate waste bin for households as well as punish offenders who violates sanitation laws and rules.

References

- Aboulnaga, M. M., Badran, M. F., & Barakat, M. M. (2021). Global informal settlements and urban slums in cities and the coverage. In M. M. Aboulnaga, M. F. Badran, & M. M. Barakat (Eds.), *Resilience of Informal Areas in Megacities – Magnitude, Challenges, and Policies: Strategic Environmental Assessment and Upgrading Guidelines to Attain Sustainable Development Goals* (pp. 1–51). Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-87794-1_1
- Alabi, J. O. (2010). *Nigeria and environmental sanitation*. Nigerian Masterweb. http://nigerianmasterweb.com/index.php/2010/10/05/title_10
- Antwi-Agyei, P., Monney, I., Amaning Adjei, K., Kweyu, R., & Simiyu, S. (2022). Shared but clean household toilets: What makes this possible? Evidence from Ghana and Kenya. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 19(7), 4271.
- Awunyo-Akaba, Y., et al. (2016). Sanitation investments in Ghana: An ethnographic investigation of the role of tenure security, land ownership and livelihoods. *BMC Public Health*, 16, 594.
- Cheng, S. (2024). Constructing a toilet standard system for the toilet revolution in China. *Journal of Water, Sanitation and Hygiene for Development*, 14(4), 291–301.
- Corburn, J., & Sverdlik, A. (2019). Informal settlements and human health. In M. Nieuwenhuijsen & H. Khreis (Eds.), *Integrating Human Health into Urban and Transport Planning: A Framework* (pp. 155–171). Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-74983-9_9
- Evans, B., et al. (2017). Limited services? The role of shared sanitation in the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development. *Journal of Water, Sanitation and Hygiene for Development*, 7(3), 349–351.
- Foggitt, E., Cawood, S., Evans, B., & Acheampong, P. (2019). Experiences of shared sanitation – towards a better understanding of access, exclusion and ‘toilet mobility’ in low-income urban areas. *Journal of Water, Sanitation and Hygiene for Development*, 9(3), 581–590.
- Kabange, R. S., Graham, J. P., & Nkansah, A. (2016). Sanitation system solution for Kotoko Community in Suame (Kumasi), Ghana. *American Scientific Research Journal for Engineering, Technology, and Sciences*, 16, 19–54.
- Lebu, S., Gyimah, R., Nandoya, E., Brown, J., Salzberg, A., & Manga, M. (2024). Assessment of sanitation infrastructure resilience to extreme rainfall and flooding: Evidence from an informal settlement in Kenya. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 354, 120264.
- Manga, M., Evans, B., & Bartram, J. (2019). Economic cost analysis of low-cost sanitation technology options in informal settlement areas (case study: Soweto Johannesburg). *International Journal of Hygiene and Environmental Health*, 223, 289–298.

- Manga, M., et al. (2022). Public health performance of sanitation technologies in Tamil Nadu, India: Initial perspectives based on E. coli release. *International Journal of Hygiene and Environmental Health*, 243, 113987.
- Massa, K., et al. (2017). Contributing to the debate on categorising shared sanitation facilities as ‘unimproved’: An account based on field researchers’ observations and householders’ opinions in three regions, Tanzania. *PLoS ONE*, 12(11), e0185875.
- Oaikhena, I. M. (2023). An assessment of strategic and administrative policies towards service delivery in a bureaucratic environment: The case of Nigeria. *Global Journal of Arts, Humanities and Social Sciences*, 11(8), 1–11.
- Park, J. E. (2011). *Textbook of Preventive and Social Medicine* (21st ed.). Bhanot Publishers.
- Prüss-Ustün, A. (2019). Burden of disease from inadequate water, sanitation and hygiene for selected adverse health outcomes: An updated analysis with a focus on low- and middle-income countries. *International Journal of Hygiene and Environmental Health*, 222(5), 765–777.
- Ross, I., et al. (2022). Impact of a sanitation intervention on quality of life and mental well-being in low-income urban neighbourhoods of Maputo, Mozambique: An observational study. *BMJ Open*, 12(9), e062517.
- Schelbert, V., et al. (2021). Quality determinants of shared sanitation facilities in low-income urban settlements. *Water Science Policy*. <https://doi.org/10.53014/HZGG5241>
- Simiyu, S., Antwi-Agyei, P., Adjei, K., & Kweyu, R. (2021). Developing and testing strategies for improving cleanliness of shared sanitation in low-income settlements of Kisumu, Kenya. *American Journal of Tropical Medicine and Hygiene*, 105(6), 1816–1825.
- Sprouse, L., et al. (2024). Shared sanitation in informal settlements: A systematic review and meta-analysis of prevalence, preferences, and quality. *International Journal of Hygiene and Environmental Health*, 260, 114392.
- Tidwell, J. B., et al. (2021). Where shared sanitation is the only immediate option: A research agenda for shared sanitation in densely populated low-income urban settings. *American Journal of Tropical Medicine and Hygiene*, 104(2), 429–432.
- UNICEF & World Health Organization. (2012). *Progress on Drinking Water and Sanitation: 2012 Update*. WHO Press.
- UNICEF & World Health Organization. (2023). *Progress on Household Drinking Water, Sanitation and Hygiene 2000–2022: Special Focus on Gender*. World Health Organization. <https://data.unicef.org/resources/jmp-report-2023/>
- Vanguard. (2013, March). *Sanitation: Nigeria loses N455bn annually - UNICEF*. <https://www.vanguardngr.com/2012/03/sanitation-nigeria-loses-n455bn-annually-unicef/>
- World Health Organization. (2012). *Global Task Force on Cholera Control: Cholera Country Profile*. http://www.who.int/features/factfiles/environmental_health/en/

World Health Organization. (2013). *Environmental Sanitation and Hygiene Development*. World Health Organization.